

List of characters

- 0) Length of antennae: (0) longer than half the length of thorax; (1) shorter than half the length of thorax
- 1) Flattened scales in the wing: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 2) Amount of scales: (0) concentrated in costal and radial sector; (1) uniformly distributed in the wing
- 3) Cross-vein sc-r: (0) present; (1) absent.
- 4) Cross-vein m-m: (0) present; (1) absent.
- 5) Vein M_{3+4} : (0) bifurcated in M_3 and M_4 ; (1) non-bifurcated.
- 6) Vein M_{1+2} : (0) bifurcated in M_1 and M_2 ; (1) non-bifurcated.
- 7) Length of the base of the vein M_{1+2} : (0) longer than twice the length of r-m; (1) shorter than twice the length of r-m.
- 8) End of vein Sc: (0) proximal to the level of end of CuP; (1) distal to the level of end of CuP.
- 9) Shape of vein R_{2+3} : (0) vertical; (1) horizontal or very inclined.
- 10) Insertion of cross-vein m-cu: (0) in vein M_{3+4} ; (1) in bM; (2) at the fork of bM.
- 11) Dorsal margin of anepisternum: (0) with 2 projections; (1) with 3 projections.
- 12) Length of last palpomere: (0) shorter than twice the length of third palpomere; (1) twice the length of third palpomere.
- 13) Male tergite X: (0) without an expanded lobule; (1) with an expanded lobule.
- 14) Left interbase: (0) pointed to the right; (1) pointed to the left.
- 15) Right interbase: (0) pointed to the left; (1) pointed to the right.
- 16) Anterior margin of paramere: (0) with 1 point; (1) with 2 points.
- 17) Width of the base of gonocoxite: (0) less than 1.5 times the width of middle; (1) more than 1.5 times the width of middle.
- 18) Length of projection of the sheath of aedeagus: (0) longer than tips; (1) as long as tips.
- 19) Connection of interbases: (0) forming a bridge; (1) not fused in a bridge
- 20) Width of interbase bridge: (0) thinner than aedeagus apex; (1) thicker than aedeagus apex.
- 21) Shape of igs: (0) straight; (1) curved.
- 22) Length of ogs: (0) as long as igs; (1) shorter than igs; (2) longer than igs.
- 23) Distal section of ventral margin of hypoginial valvae: (0) without projections; (1) with a projection.
- 24) Length of dorsal margin of female sternite IX: (0) shorter than twice of ventral margin; (1) longer than twice of ventral margin.

Phylogenetic matrix

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	0123456789012345678901234
<i>Aphrophila (M.) chilena</i>	00-000111-20000011000--0?
<i>Amphineurus (R.) nothofagetorum</i>	00-011011010000011-1-0100
<i>Amphineurus (A.) umbraticus</i>	00-01101101000001101-12??
<i>Molophilus (M.) lindi</i>	00-010101010000000-1-0100
<i>Molophilus (S.) barringtonensis</i>	00-01010101?000000-1-000?
<i>M. (H.) christelae</i> sp. n.	01001011012?1?????0?10??
<i>M. (M.) dextra</i>	111110111101110101000111?
<i>M. (M.) edwardsi</i>	1111101101001100110011000
<i>M. (M.) sinistra</i>	1111101111011110111011001
<i>M. (M.) squamigera</i>	1111111001001101100001110
<i>M. (M.) trimedia</i>	1111101101011111111011101

Phylogenetic analysis

Fig. 1. Resultant 1 MPT. Same topology with Equal Weighting and Implied Weighting (k=3). Analysis made by TNT [94], 10,000 trees holding 100. CI = 0.68; RI = 0.78.